

Diagnosis Of *Phytophthora*: A Devastating Fungus Of Citrus Using Different Approaches.

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Abstract:

Citrus is most popular and economical fruit crops of the world. It is cultivated in around 145 countries, including many in the Asia-Pacific. Its is popular because of its high nutritional value. During recent years, there has been significant increase in the citrus production mainly on account of its increased use as nutritious and healthy drink, but with increasing area production has been lower down because of several reasons including attack of diseases and pest. Among all diseases *phytophthora* causes 80 to 100 % economic losses to grower. For better control management there is need of correct diagnosis. The present study was designed to develop correct diagnosis methods using different approaches. Infected samples were collected from field. From the samples *phytophthora* was isolated and purified using PARPH-CMA medium. The rDNA was amplified using universal primer *i.e* ITS and the amplicon was sequenced and further primers were designed using primer-3 and validated using PCR method and we found set of primer detect only *phytophthora* from soil and infected root samples. Monoclonal antibodies were raised using hybridoma technology and used for standardization of ELISA. While proceeding with work we were able to diagnosis lowest density of *phytophthora* in field. As well as using this approach field soil had been tested for presence of *phytophthora*. This diagnosis method helps in the identification and screening of diseased planting material from nursery. For better orchard there is need for soil as well as planting material testing for disease control management. So this is very quick, accurate and sensitive method for detection of *phytophthora* which is national problem for citrus growing industry.

Key words: Citrus diseases, Diagnosis, gummosis, PCR, *Phytophthora spp.*, ITS – internal transcribed spacer, ELISA

Introduction:

The genus *Citrus* is economically very important and is known for its juice and pulp throughout the world. It is an important group of plants which has influenced the life of the people throughout the world. India ranks 6th position in the production of citrus fruit cultivation in the world. From last ten years citrus growing area has been increased about 20.3% and production by 20.9. Mandarin sweet oranges, lemons, lime are major citrus fruits taken in India. At present citrus production is about 11.14 Million MT with maximum share of sweet oranges followed by mandarin and acid lime. In India, there are 26 states involved in citrus production but 9 states covers more than 90%of area with 89% of total production. Maharashtra state rank first in area but production it is fourth and productivity it's far below. The lower in productivity is because of diseases and pest attack. Citrus diseases can be broadly categorized as (a) fungal (b) bacterial (c) viral and (d) mycoplasma disease. In which fungal diseases are gummosis (Causal organism. *Phytophthora species*), pink disease, powdery

mildew, citrus scab, anthracnose or wither tip, twig blight or citrus, sooty mould, bacterial diseases like citrus canker and virus and mycoplasma diseases are tristeza virus, greening disease, citrus mosaic, psorosis disease. Among which most damaging one are Gummosis and Tristeza virus causes serious losses in production (Francesco et al., 2015).

An extensive roving survey was conducted in different districts of Marathwada region of Maharashtra state to isolate the pathogen associated with the gummosis of sweet orange. In all 103 sweet orange orchards surveyed the average disease incidence of 38.83 per cent had been observed. Peak period of disease expression was August-September that was concomitant with heavy rainfall, high humidity percentage and temperature range of 18 °C – 35 °C. The harvest of disease free fruits was increased in adopted orchards (Jagtap, 2012) The most important species include *Phytophthora parasitica* Dastur (*P. nicotianae*), *P. citrophthora* and *P. palmivora*. *P. parasitica* has been reported to cause citrus diseases in India (Kamat, 1927;;

Naqvi, 1988; Naqvi, 2000b) and). More than 20 per cent plants die due to this pathogen in citrus nurseries of central India where 7-8 million citrus plants are being propagated every year. Rest of the apparently healthy plants from such infected nurseries becomes the primary source of spread of this pathogen to new areas (Das, 2009).

For control management there is need of appropriate diagnosis of disease. But for a healthy it's better to prevent disease than controlling if it. Recently many methods are developed to detect phytophthora. In this sense, Martin et al. (2002) reported a comparison among hybridization probes, RT-PCR and serological techniques, concluding that ELISA was the most sensitive and universal method for pathogen detection. Many species of *Phytophthora* can now be identified using their unique DNA sequences in the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) regions of their nuclear ribosomal DNA (rDNA) repeat region. Recently, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) has been used extensively for the detection of plant pathogens. *Phytophthora* is a major problem for growing citrus industry not only in Maharashtra but worldwide, so there are needs to develop an appropriate diagnosis method for control management. *Phytophthora* is a pseudofungus requires different management practices than other fungi. For control of phytophthora there is need of correct diagnosis in early stage with accurate and less expensive keeping this objective as priority this study was carried out using further mentioned methodology.

Materials and methods

Source of isolates and DNA extraction

Phytophthora spp. Isolated from soil samples were collected from various citrus growing orchards in Vidarbha region of Maharashtra

Soil samples were collected from rhizosphere of each plant at 5 to 30 cm depth along with feeder roots. Samples were diluted by adding 20 cc soil in 80ml of sterile distilled water and plated on a selective medium plate containing Pimaricin, Ampicilin, Rifamicin, penta-chloronitrobenzene and himexazol (PARPH) at a specific concentration of each antibiotic into corn meal agar medium (Kannwischer and Michell, 1978). Typical muddy colonies of *Phytophthora* were observed on specific medium and those colonies were then purified on PARPH-CMA selective plate. *Phytophthora* colonies were

maintained on corn meal agar plate and in sterile distilled water vials for long term storage. Majorly found fungus species in citrus orchard isolated in this research programme are *Fusarium spp.*,

For DNA extraction After vacuum filtration, the mycelium was freeze-dried for extended storage at -20 °C. To extract total DNA 10–20 mg of dry mycelia were crushed with liquid nitrogen and then suspended in 1:2 of extraction buffer (200 mM Tri-HCl [pH 8], 250 mM NaCl, 25 mM EDTA, 0.2% CTAB), vials were kept in water bath for 60min at 65⁰c and centrifuged with 13,000 rpm. The supernatant precipitated with 800 µl of phenol/chloroform/isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1) and centrifuged at 13,000 ×g for 5 min. The aqueous phase was extracted twice with 800µl of phenol/chloroform/isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1) and 700 µl of chloroform/isoamyl alcohol (24:1), respectively. DNA was precipitated with an equal volume of isopropanol for 1 h at 4 °C, then pellet was washed with 70% cold ethanol (-20 °C), dried, resuspended in sterile distilled water and stored at -20 °C. For routine amplifications, DNA was diluted to 50 ng/µl and maintained at 4 °C deep freeze.

PCR amplification

To ensure the quality of template DNA, all extracts were amplified by PCR with universal primers i.e ITS1-ITS4 combination. PCR reactions were performed in a total volume of 25 µl containing 50 ng of genomic DNA, 10mM Tris-HCl (pH 9), 50mM KCl, 0.1% Triton X-100, 100 µM dNTPs, 1mMMgCl₂, 1 unit of *Taq* polymerase (*Taq* DNA polymerase, Promega Corporation, WI, USA) and 2 µM of primers. The PCR reaction was incubated in a programmable thermal cycler starting with 5 min denaturation at 95°C, followed by 35 cycles at 95°C for 30s, annealing at 56°C for 45s, and extension at 72°C for 1 min. A negative control (no template DNA present in PCR reaction) was included in all experiments. Amplicons were analyzed by electrophoresis in 2% agarose gels in TBE and visualized by staining with ethidium bromide. The amplified product was sent for sequencing and sequenced products were analyzed using sequencer analyzer and specific primers were designed for phytophthora diagnosis.

Antiserum production:

New Zealand white rabbit was injected with five 0.5ml virus injections at weekly intervals. The first was with equal volume of Freund's complete adjuvant and subsequent ones with Freund's incomplete adjuvant. Test bleed was done after the fourth injection, after a ten day gap the final injection was given and final bleeding was done at an interval of ten days. The serum was separated after overnight incubation at room temperature and antiserum collected (van Regenmortel, 1982; Muske et al., 2014).

Standardization of Indirect and Direct Dot Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (DIBA):

Indirect and Direct Dot- ELISA was standardized using 2µl of suitably diluted antigen (crude mycelia extract), following the procedure described by Timmer (1993) with few modifications. The antiserum dilutions used for both Direct and Indirect DIBA were 1:500, 1:1000, 1:2000, 1:4000, 1:8000, 1:16000 and 1:32000 the dilutions of antigen used were 1:10, 1:20 and 1:50 and healthy control, secondary antibody was used at a dilution of 1:1000 and 1:2000.

Standardization of Direct and Indirect Plate Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA):

Plate ELISA was standardized on polystyrene plates by following a modified protocol described by Clark and Adams (1977). The antiserum dilutions used for both Direct and Indirect plate ELISA were 1:500, 1:1000, 1:2000, 1:4000, 1:8000, 1:16000 and 1:32000, dilutions of antigen used were 1:10, 1:20 and 1:50 and healthy control with secondary antibody dilutions of 1:1000 and 1:2000. The optical density (OD) readings were recorded at 405 nm.

Results and Discussion

For disease management purposes, it is frequently desirable to know whether *Phytophthora spp.* are present and if so, at

what level. Fruit and leaf baiting methods were developed many years ago for detection of *Phytophthora spp.* (Klotz et al., 1958). These are usually considered qualitative tests, but propagule densities can be quantified by use of more complex techniques. They are relatively simple and require minimal equipment and supplies. PCR was carried using ITS1-ITS4 primer and the PCR profiling shown in fig.2. The PCR products were sequenced by eurofines, Hyderabad. With 98% sequence similarity with NCBI database and specific primers were designed for available sequence and further validated with *phytophthora* and other constrictant as shown in fig.3. The designed primer can detect only *phytophthora spp.* at minimal density.

Direct and Indirect Dot- ELISA was standardized by dotting suitably diluted primary antibody and antigen in coating buffer onto nitrocellulose membrane respectively. A titer of 1:32000 of primary antibody, 1:50 of antigen, and 1:2000 of secondary antibody was found appropriate to detect *Phytophthora* in direct and indirect dot ELISA with no colour seen in control as shown in fig.4.

In the plate ELISA standardization experiment, colour development was observed in all combinations of the primary antibody, antigen and secondary antibody dilutions. A titre of 1:50 dilution of antigen, 1:16000 of primary antibody and 1:2000 of secondary antibody dilution was fixed for indirect plate ELISA with an optimum OD reading of 1.016 at 405 nm. No color was observed in control as shown in Fig.4.

Future work will have to be focused on characterizing and grouping of strains and development of immunodiagnostic strips for rapid detection of *phytophthora* in the field and in nursery which controls spread of inoculums to healthy orchard.

Fig.1 Amplification Profiling of isolates of *Phytophthora* from different locations using specific primer (L- 100 bp Ladder, P1-Nagpur , P2-Varud , P3- Katol, P4-Amravati, P5-Achalpur , P6-Akola).

Fig.2 Amplified product of PCR with specific primer pair ITS1-ITS4 (Lane1-marker, 2- non template control, A-pure culture of *P.*

nicotianae B- Infected soil sample, C-infected soil sample with *Fusarium* D- Sterile soil sample)

Fig. 3. Standardized DOT-ELISA for *phytophthora* detection

Fig. 4. Standardized DOT-ELISA for *phytophthora* detection

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